

End-Use Analysis of ASHRAE Standard 90.1-2019

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Abstract

This paper summarizes the analysis conducted by Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL), assessing expected end-use energy consumption in commercial buildings, based on recent editions of the model energy code for the commercial sector, ANSI/ASHRAE/IES Standard 90.1, *Energy Standard for Buildings Except Low-Rise Residential Buildings*. The results represent simulated energy use based on Commercial Prototype Building Models¹ across representative climate zones in the United States, as defined by Standard 90.1. PNNL examined the resulting simulation outputs to assess how energy is used across primary systems within prominent U.S. commercial building types to understand how energy is used in each building type at the end-use level and to identify areas for improvements in future code cycles.

Background:

The national model energy standard for commercial buildings in the United States is ANSI/ASHRAE/IES Standard 90.1, *Energy Standard for Buildings Except Low-Rise Residential Buildings* (hereafter referred to as Standard 90.1). Standard 90.1, first published in 1975 (originally referred to as Standard 90) provides minimum energy efficiency guidelines for designing, constructing, operating, and maintaining new construction and renovation buildings. It is updated continuously, with new editions published every 3 years. When each new edition of the Standard is published energy and cost savings impacts are quantified by Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) for the U.S. Department of Energy Building Energy Codes Program² by performing building energy simulations of prototype building energy models¹ constructed to the previous and new edition. The previously published report '*Energy Savings Analysis: ANSI/ASHRAE/IES Standard 90.1-2019*'³ in support of DOE's Determination^a details the qualitative and quantitative comparison of Standard 90.1-2019 to Standard 90.1-2016 to determine its energy savings impacts. The current paper is a detailed review of the simulation results that formed the basis of the Energy Savings Analysis report. The objective is to discern how compliance with Standard 90.1-2019 impacts energy use in prototypical newly constructed commercial buildings by energy end-use, building

^a The Energy Conservation and Production Act (42 U.S.C. 6831 et seq.) establishes requirements for DOE to review consensus-based building energy conservation standards and provides that whenever Standard 90.1 is revised, the Secretary of Energy must make a determination whether the revised code would improve energy efficiency in commercial buildings.

type, and climate zones in the United States. This paper aims to provide ASHRAE technical committees and other interested parties a better understanding of how the Standard affects various building systems and end uses, specifically, those in the Standard that most prominently influence energy efficiency. Additionally, findings from this study can provide industry stakeholders guidance in identifying building types and end-uses with the most potential for energy efficiency improvements through energy codes and those that may require beyond code measures to meet energy use reduction targets.

Methodology:

Per the report, *'Energy Savings Analysis: ANSI/ASHRAE/IES Standard 90.1-2019'*³ compliance with Standard 90.1-2019 results in nationwide savings of 4.7% for site energy, 4.3% for source energy, 4.3% for energy cost, and 4.2% for carbon emissions compared to Standard 90.1-2016. The quantitative analysis in that report provides stakeholders involved in the standard development process with a formal mechanism to track energy reduction targets. The report and the study are based on large-scale simulation of prototypical building energy models to approximate the typical energy consumption of commercial buildings in the United States. The 16 prototype buildings simulated in 19 ASHRAE climate zones (16 U.S. climates) represent approximately 75% of the total floor area of commercial construction in the United States⁴. The technical specifications of the prototype models, including envelope type, HVAC system configuration, and operational characteristics, are intended to represent typical buildings; hence they do not cover all combinations of building systems prevalent in commercial buildings. Inputs gathered from subject matter experts and committee members of ASHRAE technical working groups inform the technical specifications of the prototypes^{5,6}. Each prototypical model represents characteristic building classes from the classification scheme established in the 2003 DOE/Energy Information Administration Commercial Building Energy Consumption Survey⁷ plus residential multifamily buildings more than three stories. In addition to Standard 90.1-2019 and Standard 90.1-2016, the study includes energy simulations representing 90.1-2013, 90.1-2010, 90.1-2007, and 90.1-2004. This paper takes the results from the 1,824 parametric EnergyPlus™⁸ simulations from the 'Energy Savings Analysis' study and analyzes them further with Python and R scripts by end-use and building group.

The 16 building prototypes represent eight major building groups – Office, Warehouse, Retail, Hotel, Apartment, School, Medical, and Restaurant. The results from EnergyPlus simulations are broken down

to these major end-use categories^b: Interior Lighting (Light.Int), Exterior Lighting (Light.Ext), Service Hot Water (SHW), Heating (Heat), Cooling (Cool), Fans & Auxiliaries (Fan.Aux), Miscellaneous (Misc) and Equipment (Equip)⁹. The results presented in this paper are a review of the simulation results aggregated by building type, building group, end-use, climate zone, and metric, and a discussion about the progress made by Standard 90.1 since the 2004 edition and opportunities for future energy codes.

Table 1: Overview of Standard 90.1 Prototype Models

Building Activity Group	Prototype Building	Number of Floors	Prototype Floor Area (ft ²)	Energy Cost Intensity (\$/sq ft/yr)	Energy Use Intensity (kBtu/sq ft/yr)
Office	Small Office	1	5,502	0.780	25.6
	Medium Office	3	53,628	0.850	29.7
	Large Office	12	498,588	1.608	53.2
Retail	Stand-Alone Retail	1	24,692	1.107	46.1
	Strip Mall	1	22,500	1.341	51.0
Education	Primary School	1	73,959	1.062	40.9
	Secondary School	2	210,887	0.946	35.6
Lodging	Outpatient Health Care	3	40,946	2.821	104.5
	Hospital	5	241,501	2.742	105.4
Hotel	Small Hotel	4	43,202	1.136	52.2
	Large Hotel	6	122,120	1.673	75.8
Warehouse	Non-Refrigerated Warehouse	1	52,045	0.334	15.5
	Warehouse				
Food Service	Quick-service Restaurant	1	2,501	8.620	492.5
	Restaurant				
	Full-service Restaurant	1	5,502	6.573	335.5
Apartment	Mid-Rise Apartment	4	33,741	1.078	36.5
	High-Rise Apartment	10	84,360	0.934	40.5

The simulated results weighted by construction weighting factors provide an estimated impact of the Standard on newly constructed and renovated commercial buildings in the United States. Data from the Dodge Data & Analytics Construction Projects Starts Database were used in the previously developed

^b Major end-use categories are comprised of following sub-end-use categories: Heat- space heating, humidification and dehumidification; Cool-space cooling and heat rejection; Fan.Aux – fans, heat recovery, pumps; Misc- elevator, refrigeration and transformers; Equip – cooking, plug loads and computer room and telephone equipment.

weighting factors⁴. The prototypes are aggregated into principle building activity groups as shown in Table 1. The Apartment group has the highest volume of floor space, followed by Warehouse, Schools, Retail, Office, Medical, Hotel, and Restaurant buildings. In the subsequent sections, results noted as weighted by building type use disaggregated weighting factors by climate zone and building type. Results presented by building groups use partial weighting applied proportionately to building types under the same grouping. For instance, to find the end-use costs for the Office type, the end-use costs for the large, medium, and small offices are weighted proportionally by the individual prototype construction weightings. Energy costⁱ is determined using \$0.1063/kwh for electricity and \$0.98/therm for heating fuels^c based on the ASHRAE Standard SSPC 90.1 fuel rates approved for development of the 2019 Standard. Carbon emissions factors are assumed to be 0.707 kg CO₂/kWh for electricity and 5.3 kg CO₂/therm for gas based on the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) Greenhouse Gas Equivalencies Calculator¹⁰.

Discussion of Findings:

From the simulated results, the national weighted energy cost index (ECI) of commercial buildings in the United States built in accordance with Standard 90.1-2019 is estimated to be 1.161 \$/ft²/year. Table 2 summarizes the estimated national savings.

Table 2: Summary of National Savings of Standard 90.1-2019 from 90.1-2016

Metric	Standard 90.1-2019	Savings % from 90.1-2016
National Weighted Energy Cost	1.161 \$/ft ² /year	4.7%
National Weighted Site Energy	46.340 kBtu/ ft ² /year	5%
National Weighted Source Energy	116.03 kBtu/ ft ² /year	4.8%
National Weighted Electricity Use	9.7 kWh/ ft ² /year	4.6%
National Weighted Gas Use	0.132 therms/ ft ² /year	6.1%

Figure 1 is a graphical summary of the end-use and building group level breakdown of Standard 90.1-2019 energy cost. The area of the plot represents the simulated national building energy cost. Each color block is the contribution of a building group and end-use to the total national energy cost. The X-axis represents building groups. The width of each building group is scaled to represent the weighted share of each group to the total national building energy cost. Each color represents the eight simple end-use categories discussed in the methodology section. The area of each color block is the weighted

^c Heating is generally modeled with a natural gas source; the heating fuel rate is a blend of natural gas, oil, propane, and electricity used for heating, based on the national commercial building mix.

share of the end-use by building type to the total national energy cost. The Equip end-use in Restaurants constitute the highest ECI, followed closely by Equip end-use in Office buildings. Light.Int in Retail and SHW in Apartment buildings has the next highest energy cost impact on national totals. At the building level, the weighted ECI is highest for the Apartment building group.

Figure 1: U.S. Weighted Energy Cost by End-Use after 90.1-2019

Energy Cost Index Breakdown by End-Use: **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the national weighted site energy and energy cost of U.S commercial buildings built to Standard 90.1-2019 broken down by end-use. For both metrics, the largest contribution comes from the Equip end-use which is currently unregulated by Standard 90.1. For loads directly regulated by Standard 90.1; Cool and Light end-uses constitute the highest share of the total simulated national building energy cost. For site energy, Heat, Cool and SHW are the largest end-uses on a national scale.

Figure 2: Weighted Energy Cost and Site Energy Breakdown by End-Use

Energy Cost Index Breakdown by Building Group: The simulated results aggregated by building group identify contributions by building group to the national weighted ECI in \$/ft²/year. For 90.1-2019, Apartment is the largest contributor, a detailed breakdown is provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Energy Cost Index Breakdown by Building Group

Building Group ^d	Energy Cost Index	% of Total Commercial Energy Cost
Apartment	0.24 \$/ft ² /year	20%
Medical	0.22 \$/ft ² /year	19%
Retail	0.17 \$/ft ² /year	15%
School	0.15 \$/ft ² /year	13%
Office	0.13 \$/ft ² /year	12%
Food Service	0.09 \$/ft ² /year	8%
Hotel	0.08 \$/ft ² /year	8%
Warehouse	0.06 \$/ft ² /year	5%

Review of Standards progression: In this section, we review the weighted ECI of six consecutive editions of Standard 90.1 to identify trends in the Standard 90.1 progression. Figure 3 shows the energy cost breakdown by end use and building activity group for 90.1-2004, 90.1-2007, 90.1-2010, 90.1-2013, 90.1-2016, and 90.1-2019. The comparison shows steady savings achieved between consecutive code

^d Excluding the “other” building group category which represents ~ 25% of U.S commercial building stock.

cycles, with the largest savings magnitude in the 2010 code cycle. Each bar represents the composite weighted national ECI for a code edition; color blocks in each bar represent the contribution of a building group (top row) and end-use (bottom row) toward the composite national ECI. Note that despite being the second largest construction floor space by volume, the weighted ECI of the Warehouse building group is the least of all. The comparison in the top row of Figure 3 indicates with each edition of the code ECI reductions are achieved across all building groups. The bottom row shows that the Interior Lighting and Space Cooling end-uses have achieved the most energy cost reductions since 2004. Future codes and standards that influence energy consumption in Apartment and Medical buildings and measures that impact equipment and space cooling end-uses can have the most significant potential for overall national energy use reduction. Also noteworthy is that more aggressive measures are required in future codes to achieve significant savings reductions and to bring the current site energy use (46.3 kBtu/ft²/year) close to net-zero goals.

Figure 3: National Weighted Energy Cost Index: Standards Progression

By fuel type: Next, we look at the impact of the Standard by fuel type. Building electrification and decarbonization policies are expected to shift fuel consumption in newly constructed commercial buildings toward higher electric use. This analysis does not consider these future trends. Instead, we analyze the simulation results by major fuel type – Electricity and Natural Gas – and compare the percent savings achieved by Standard 90.1-2019 to 90.1-2016 and 90.1-2004. Figure 4 shows the percent savings of Standard 90.1-2019 from 90.1-2016 (as dark dots) and percent savings from 90.1-2004 (as pale dots). Note that of the total simulated weighted national energy use, roughly 92% is from electric end uses, and the remaining is gas. An overall nationwide savings of 37.4% have been achieved in electric and 37.8% in gas weighted energy use intensity compared to 90.1-2004. Compared to 90.1-2016, savings achieved are 4.6% in electric use and 6.1% in gas use intensity. Carbon emission

reductions of 37% from 90.1-2004 and roughly 5% from 90.1-2016 can be achieved by Standard 90.1-2019. The rate of carbon emission reduction and electricity savings from 90.1-2016 is within 10% and gas savings is within 15% for all prototypes. The range is much wider (20% to 65%) for savings from the 90.1-2004 edition, indicating that the newer editions of Standard 90.1 have covered a broader range of measures impacting all types of buildings compared to older editions.

Figure 4: Percent Savings Comparison by Carbon Emission and Site Energy by Fuel Type for Standard 90.1-2019 vs 90.1-2004 and 90.1-2016.

Contribution of Space Heating and Cooling to National Weighted Energy Cost: Space heating and cooling energy consumption are highly sensitive to climate conditions. Buildings in cold climates like ASHRAE climate zones 7 and 8 see higher energy usage for space heating than other parts of the country. In comparison buildings in warm ASHRAE climate zones like 0, 1 and 2 see higher cooling

energy use. However the volume of projected new construction activities varies, with largest activity in Climate zones 2, 3, 4 and 5⁴. We overlay the construction weights to heating and cooling energy by climate zone to estimate net contribution to overall national weighted energy cost. Figure 5 shows the contributions by climate zone classified by ASHRAE moisture regimes. The weighted contribution is highest from the moist (A) climates for both heating and cooling. This is due to larger populations in the A climate zones and increased energy use due to higher humidity. Cooling in climate zone 2A and heating in 5A have the most significant impact on overall national energy cost because of the combination of environmental factors and high construction volume. Hence, future energy codes that target energy use reductions in climate zones 2A and 5A can have a more considerable effect on overall national energy cost than extreme climate zones like 1, 7, or 8.

Figure 5: Contribution of Weighted Heating and Cooling ECI to National Energy Cost by Climate Zone

To evaluate the prescriptive insulation requirements in Standard 90.1 (based on space conditioning categories; non-residential, residential, and semi-heated), the heating and cooling data is split by building category and climate zone (without moisture regimes). Figure 6 shows weighted heating and cooling energy cost indices by climate zone. The residential category includes apartments and hotels, the semi-heated category includes warehouses, and the non-residential category includes all other prototypes. Although some residential areas exist in hospitals, some non-residential regions of large

hotels, and only about half of the warehouse prototypes are semi-heated, the grouping used in *Figure 6* is based on the predominant category in each building type. The main conclusion is that reducing heating energy use in climate zone 5 and reducing cooling energy use in zones 2 and 3 for all three building categories have the most potential for overall U.S. energy cost savings.

Figure 6: Contribution of Weighted Heating and Cooling ECI to National Cost by Building Classification

Conclusions:

- Unregulated equipment represents the top end-use in U.S. buildings constructed to Standard 90.1-2019. As the Standard gets more efficient, the importance of reducing unregulated equipment gains even more prominence. If aggressive energy and emissions targets are to be achieved, building codes will need an increased focus on building loads that are currently unregulated. Alternatively, new approaches will need to be developed to influence their energy use reduction. For example, over recent code cycles elevators, commercial refrigeration, computer room cooling systems, industrial laboratory fume hoods, and residential lighting have all become regulated. Further expansion to commercial cooking equipment, compressed air systems, and other industrial processes is being considered. Additional supporting efforts might include adding submetering or measurement and verification requirements for unregulated loads. Codes might also address additional unregulated loads if their reduction can be indicated on construction drawings and verified by field inspection or via performance-based standards.

- Space cooling and lighting are the top two regulated end-uses remaining after Standard-90.1-2019. Future code changes directly impacting these two end-uses will have an important impact on reducing the national energy cost of commercial buildings. Apartment and Medical buildings are top candidates for further national energy use reductions.
- Considering currently regulated loads, code changes that directly impact heating in climate zone 5 and cooling in zones 2 and 3 have the most significant potential for nationwide savings.
- Although not directly evaluated in the current analysis, equipment building energy use cannot be eliminated and renewable energy generation, demand response and other load management strategies will need to be included in future energy codes if net-zero energy and net-zero emission energy code goals are to be met.

Additional Information: A supplemental Excel workbook containing detailed results for each prototype at the detailed end-use level is available at:

<https://www.energycodes.gov/sites/default/files/documents/2019EndUseTables.zip>

The workbook contains a worksheet for each prototype and a matrix of tables with summary national results and detailed results for each climate zone. In addition to ECI, site energy use index (EUI) results, source EUI results, and gas and electric end-use results are included. An open-source webpage featuring the data and additional analysis is available at

<https://public.tableau.com/app/profile/doebecp/viz/2019EndUseAnalysisViz-Copy/Introduction>.

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